

Composite curved hourglass cellular structures: design optimization for stiffness response and crashworthiness performance

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Abstract

Auxetic lattice structures are known for their superior stiffness-to-density and strength-to-density ratios. Re-entrant hourglass exhibits an acceptable equivalent elastic modulus and remarkable energy absorption capacity among various auxetic configurations due to their flexibility and hinge deflecting during crushing loads. This study introduces a curved hourglass honeycomb which can be produced using 3D printing with pure or reinforced filaments incorporating continuous fibers. New closed-form formulations are analytically derived using an energy method by considering an extracted unit cell to predict the equivalent in-plane mechanical properties for the first time. The plateau stress of the proposed honeycomb is evaluated at the densification state of a unit cell using the energy conservation theory, equating external work with plastic energy dissipation. The accuracy of these extended relations is validated against experimental outcomes, demonstrating good agreement between analytical and experimental results. Additionally, robust linear and nonlinear finite element analyses are conducted to assess the accuracy of the obtained relations, including the equivalent stiffness and plateau stress for structures produced with reinforced filaments. The nonlinear finite element code employs appropriate subroutines to model plasticity/damage events. Based on the established analytical relations for stiffness and plateau stress, multi-objective optimization using Genetic Algorithm is applied to define optimum values for the Pareto front chart's objective functions of stiffness and plateau stress. The optimization process involves exploring the design space and defining the values of geometrical parameters to achieve the desired objectives. In conclusion, this study presents a novel approach to developing curved re-entrant honeycomb structures, with analytical formulations validated against experimental and numerical results. Optimization helps to identify optimal configurations concerning stiffness and plateau stress, offering potential applications in lightweight and high-strength materials design.

Keywords: Equivalent stiffness, Curved hourglass, Plateau stress, Energy method, Experiments, Optimization.

1. Introduction

Cellular structures are widely utilized for weight reduction in several applications, including enhancing impact resistance in vehicles [1], reinforcing airplane wings [2], and serving as medical implants [3]. Two-dimensional planar cellular structures are commonly referred to as honeycombs [4]-[7], regardless of whether they adopt the traditional hexagonal topology found in bees' honeycombs. Many honeycomb topologies have been proposed, featuring straight elements like hexagonal, triangular, and square arrangements [8]. The literature reveals a considerable focus on investigating the mechanical behavior of honeycombs through the development of analytical and computational models, alongside standardized mechanical tests [9]. Ongaro [10] conducted a review of the analytical modeling of honeycombs' mechanical properties, highlighting two primary methods of analysis: structural analysis-based [11] and energy equivalence-based [12]. The mechanical response of honeycombs can be influenced by the bending or stretching of individual elements comprising the unit cell, often represented as beams. Gibson et al. [13] utilized beam theory to derive expressions that relate the geometric parameters of the hexagonal honeycomb to its effective stiffness and strength. Wang and McDowell [14] summarized the effective mechanical properties of honeycomb structures, with volume fraction as a key factor, obtained by analyzing stresses in each strut. Dos Reis and Ganghoffer [15] employed micropolar elasticity theory to obtain stiffness matrices for triangular, square, and hexagonal

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lattices. This theory assumes that the elements forming the lattice arrangements are small compared to the macro dimensions of the external volume, and it incorporates coupled stresses to enhance the accuracy of analytical predictions [16].

Auxetic honeycomb lattice structures have recently emerged as a promising solution to enhance energy absorption properties [17]- [19]. These structures exhibit a negative Poisson's ratio behavior, meaning they contract in the transverse direction when subjected to compression. As a result, they offer significant resistance to crushing forces by deforming toward the impact area rather than flowing away from it [20]. Additionally, their hollow configuration presents excellent potential for lightweight design. Numerous researchers have investigated the static and dynamic crashing response of auxetic honeycombs [21], but many studies are constrained by manufacturing limitations, primarily focusing on isotropic materials and simple configurations. Yang et al. [22] utilized the Timoshenko beam model to explore the properties of auxetic structures under large deformations, developing an analytical model to analyze their response, which was verified through finite element analysis (FEA) and experiments. Li et al. [23] proposed a novel 3D re-entrant cellular specimen (ARCS) and applied classical beam theory to determine the mechanical properties in principal directions, revealing superior negative Poisson's ratio and enhanced elastic modulus in these directions, albeit with low elastic modulus in off-axis directions. Fu et al. [24] proposed a honeycomb structure with enhanced mechanical properties by embedding a rhombic scheme inside a re-entrant hexagonal honeycomb. Numerical simulations and theoretical analysis were employed to evaluate the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio under compression loading, demonstrating a higher elastic modulus than the simple re-entrant hexagonal honeycomb. Fu et al. [25] also suggested an enhanced auxetic honeycomb with the rhombus embedded into the typical re-entrant hexagonal honeycomb, developing an analytical model to assess the mechanical properties and post-buckling response under uniaxial compression load, validated through FEA. Grima et al. [26] examined the mechanical properties of re-entrant and conventional hexagonal honeycombs, considering the shape and thickness of the ligaments through an analytical model. They proposed an extended version of existing analytical models, accounting for the impact of ligaments' finite thickness on the structure's response. Scarpa et al. [27] conducted FEA to analyze the Poisson's ratio and elastic modulus of re-entrant honeycombs with various layout combinations under uniaxial loading, obtaining satisfactory agreement with experimental findings. Wan et al. [28] developed a theoretical model using the large deflection beam model to evaluate the negative Poisson's ratios of auxetic honeycombs, also analyzing the effect of geometric parameters of the unit cell on Poisson's ratios. Hu and Deng [29] conducted a comprehensive study on the indentation resistance of re-entrant honeycombs, exploring how it varies with the cell wall angle. Their investigation utilized both analytical and numerical approaches to derive an analytical model for determining the Poisson's ratio and elastic modulus. To validate their findings, experimental tests were carried out. Veisi and Farrokhhabadi [30] presented a novel analytical model based on classical lamination theory (CLT) to assess the in-plane mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced re-entrant structures. This analytical approach offers valuable insights into the behavior of these structures when reinforced with fibers.

Recent advancements in 3D printing techniques have paved the way for creating innovative and intricate composite structures. Akhoundi et al. [31] introduced a novel material extrusion-based printing technique for fabricating continuous fiber-reinforced composites. In this method, fibers were impregnated with melted filament within the heated nozzle of the printer just before the printing process. This approach simplifies the production of complex lattice structures using composite materials. Chao et al. [32] utilized 3D printing technology to manufacture composite re-entrant honeycombs, demonstrating that incorporating carbon fiber reinforcement significantly enhances the energy absorption capability of these lattice structures. Qi et al. [33] presented a unique circular re-entrant honeycomb printed with PLA material and explored its energy absorption performance through experimental and numerical investigations. In a performed study by Farrokhhabadi et al. [34], fiber-reinforced cruciform cell structures were thoroughly investigated under tensile loads. Their theoretical model incorporated Castigliano's second theorem and the energy method, complemented by

experimental investigations and numerical evaluations to validate the obtained results. Furthermore, Farrokhbadi et al. [35] proposed an innovative theoretical model to estimate the mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced U-type unit cells. This model involved numerical simulations and experimental tests conducted under tensile loading, contributing to a deeper understanding of the mechanical behavior of these fiber-reinforced structures.

Among various auxetic configurations, star-shaped honeycombs stand out for their superior energy absorption capacity, owing to their remarkable flexibility and hinge traveling during crushing loads, resulting from plastic deformation angles [36]. This study introduces a groundbreaking curved hourglass honeycomb (CHH), showcasing exceptional energy absorption and elastic modulus features. Hourglass honeycombs exhibit high equivalent elastic modulus compared to other structures. The aim of introducing the curved structure compared to traditional filling materials like foam and honeycomb is to increase the structure's equivalent material properties and plateau strength while maintaining a low weight. The proposed lattice structure can be also produced using 3D printing with *pure or reinforced filaments*. As illustrated in Fig. 1, this structure can be employed for fabricating automobiles' different parts. Using the energy approach, the analytical relations which give the equivalent material properties and plateau stress of structure will be extended in the first stage. Using the appropriate experiments as well as robust numerical approach, the accuracy of proposed relations will be examined in stage 2. Having the closed form relations of stiffness and plateau stress, GA is used in stage 3 to represent the Pareto Front graph. Finally, by performing the parametric study in stage 4, the design region achievable by CHH structure in Ashby Chart will be represented.

Fig. 1. Application of proposed CHH honeycomb as the different parts of automotive structures: (a) Analytical analysis of material properties and plateau stress using the energy approach, (b) Experimental and numerical studies for verification of extended analytical relations, (c) Multi-objective optimization, (d) Extraction of the design region of CHH structure in Ashby Chart.

The manuscript is organised as follows: Section 2 introduces the geometry of the structure and the extended relations for the equivalent material properties. In section 3, the details of the evaluation of plateau stress using analytical and FE approaches will be explained. Section 4 represents the details of

multi-objective optimization using Genetic Algorithm (GA). The results and discussion, including the analytical, numerical, and experimental approaches will be explained in Section 5.

2. Presentation of the structure and evaluation of equivalent material properties

As illustrated in Fig. 2, compared to the other conventional 2D lattice structures, the CHH honeycomb structure can be easily fabricated by 3D printer employing filaments reinforced by continuous fibers. The print path and geometrical parameters of a unit cell extracted from the CHH structure are shown in Fig. 2 (a) and 1(b), respectively.

Fig. 2 Configuration of CHH structure (a) Printing paths, (b) Definition of geometrical parameter on an extracted unit cell.

For more details, can refer to Fig. 2 (b); the unit cell is composed of different curved and straight struts: the horizontal straight struts like AB and CD with the length of L and L_2 , and the curved strut BC with the radius of r and angle of θ . The thickness and width of the walls are t and B , respectively. In addition,

the height of the unit cell is $2H$, and the arch angle of θ is calculated as $\alpha = \arcsin(H/r)$. It should be mentioned that for a constant length of the circumference of a unit cell i.e., $4L + 4r\theta + 2L_2$, the following constraints must be governed by the geometrical parameters to produce a reasonable geometry:

$$\begin{cases} r(1 - \cos(\theta)) < L \\ L - r(1 - \cos(\theta)) < L_2 \\ 2 < \theta < 89 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In the following, the methodology for obtaining the equivalent material properties of a CHH honeycomb, including the in-plane moduli and Poisson's ratio, relative density and plateau stress, will be presented. Given their fundamental significance, these properties play a crucial role in the design of lattice structures.

2.1 Vertical equivalent stiffness

In this section, theoretical models for the in-plane Young's modulus of the curved honeycomb will be derived using Castigliano's theorem. The CHH honeycomb block, which undergoes an external uniaxial force F in the y direction, is illustrated in Fig. 3. According to the periodicity and symmetry of the curved honeycomb, a unit cell (ABCD), as outlined by the red dotted line in Fig. 3, was determined to calculate the equivalent elastic moduli.

Fig. 3 Schematic configuration of CHH structure subjected to vertical load F .

When the CHH block is subjected to a uniaxial vertical load w , the unit cell will bear corresponding loads. In this case, the straight horizontal beam AB with the length of L , and the curved beam BC with the radius of r and angle of θ , play significant roles in the transverse vertical deflection of the unit cell. As shown in Fig. 4, one concentrated force (R_A) is acting on point A while two bending moments M_A and M_B are acting on points A and B for symmetric balance. It should be noted that while the distributed load w is an actual load only in the case of loading along the y direction, in the meantime, the dummy force F is imposed to the unit cell, so Castigliano's method can be used for calculating the y -directional strain.

Fig. 4 Applied vertical load and boundary condition for the unit cell extracted from the CHH structure, (a) Load distribution on strut AB, (b) Load distribution on strut BC.

From the force analysis in Fig. 4(a), the axial force (R_{AB}), shear force (P_{AB}) and bending moment (M_{AB}) on the wall AB can be listed as

$$\begin{cases} R_{AB} = R_A \\ P_{AB} = wx \\ M_{AB} = \frac{wx^2}{2} - M_A \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, from the force analysis in Fig.4b, the axial force (R_{BC}), shear force (P_{BC}) and bending moment (M_{BC}) on the curved wall BC can be listed as

$$\begin{cases} R_{BC} = -R_A \sin(\theta) + (wL + F) \cos(\theta) \\ P_{BC} = (wL + F) \sin(\theta) - R_A \cos(\theta) \\ M_{BC} = M_A - \frac{wL^2}{2} + (wL + F) r(1 - \cos(\theta)) - R_A r \sin(\theta) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The elastic strain energy stored in the unit cell ABCD, comprises two components.

$$\begin{aligned} U_{AB} &= \int_0^L \frac{R_{AB}^2(x)}{2E_1A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{kR_{AB}^2(x)}{2G_{12}A} dx + \\ &\int_0^L \frac{M_{AB}^2(x)}{2E_1I} dx = \int_0^L \frac{R_A^2}{2E_1A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{k(wx)^2}{2G_{12}A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{(\frac{wx^2}{2} - M_A)^2}{2E_1I} dx \\ U_{BC} &= \int_0^\theta \frac{R_{BC}^2(x)}{2E_1A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{kP_{BC}^2(x)}{2G_{12}A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{M_{BC}^2(x)}{2E_1I} r d\theta \\ &= \int_0^\theta \frac{(-R_A \sin(\theta) + (wL + F) \cos(\theta))^2}{2E_1A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{k((wL + F) \sin(\theta) - R_A \cos(\theta))^2}{2G_{12}A} r d\theta + \\ &\int_0^\theta \frac{(M_A - \frac{wL^2}{2} + (wL + F) r(1 - \cos(\theta)) - R_A r \sin(\theta))^2}{2E_1I} r d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

E_1 and G_{12} are the elastic modulus in fiber direction and in-plane shear modulus, respectively. $A = bt$ is the cross-section area of the wall, and $I = bt^3/12$ denotes the area moment of inertia. $k = 0.8$ is the shear coefficient for a rectangular cross-section.

Due to symmetric boundary conditions, horizontal displacement and in-plane rotation in point A, i.e. u_A and θ_A must be restricted. Then;

$$\begin{cases} u_A = \frac{dU_{AB}}{dR_A} + \frac{dU_{BC}}{dR_A} = 0 \\ \theta_A = \frac{dU_{AB}}{dM_A} + \frac{dU_{BC}}{dM_A} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The simultaneous solution of the abovementioned two relations results in the values of horizontal reaction force R_A , and bending moment M_A as a function of the applied concentrated load of w as

$$\begin{aligned} R_A &= f_1(w) \\ M_A &= f_2(w) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Replacing horizontal reaction force R_A , bending moment M_A into obtained strain energy results in

$$\begin{aligned} U_{AB}(w) &= \int_0^L \frac{(f_1(w))^2}{2E_1A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{k(wx)^2}{2G_{12}A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{(\frac{wx^2}{2} - f_2(w))^2}{2E_1I} dx \\ U_{BC}(w) &= \int_0^\theta \frac{(-f_1(w) \sin(\theta) + (wL+F) \cos(\theta))^2}{2E_1A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{k((wL+F) \sin(\theta) - f_1(w) \cos(\theta))^2}{2G_{12}A} r d\theta + \\ &\int_0^\theta \frac{(f_2(w) - \frac{wL^2}{2} + (wL+F)r(1-\cos(\theta)) - f_1(w)r \sin(\theta))^2}{2E_1I} r d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Now, the vertical deflection of point B could be obtained by differentiation of the total strain energy related to vertical dummy load F as

$$v_B = \left(\frac{dU_{AB}}{dF} + \frac{dU_{BC}}{dF} \right)_{F=0} \quad (8)$$

Having the vertical deflection and applied load, the vertical stiffness of the structure can be obtained as

$$E_y = \frac{Pr \sin(\theta)}{B(L - r(1 - \cos(\theta))) v_B} \quad (9)$$

It should be noted that in Eq. (9), the vertical deflection at the point of applied loading, i.e. v_B can be evaluated by Eq. (8).

2.2 Horizontal equivalent stiffness

In this section, the CHH honeycomb block, which undergoes an external uniaxial force F in the x direction, is considered for obtaining the equivalent horizontal stiffness (Fig. 5). According to the periodicity and symmetry of the curved honeycomb, a unit cell (ABCD), as outlined by the red dotted line in Fig. 5, was determined to calculate the equivalent elastic moduli. For more details, can refer to Fig. 6; while the unit cell comprises three struts, the curved beam BC, with the radius of r and angle of θ , and the straight beam BA play a significant role in the axial horizontal deflection of the unit cell. As shown in Fig. 6, one concentrated force (R_c) is acting on point C while the bending moments M_c is acting on point C for symmetric balance. Having the concentrated load P as the only actual load the case of loading along the x direction, Castigliano's method can be used to calculate the x -directional deflection.

Fig. 5 Schematic configuration of CHH structure subjected to horizontal load F .

From the force analysis in Fig. 6(a), the axial force (R_{CB}), shear force (P_{CB}) and bending moment (M_{CB}) on the wall, CB can be listed as

Fig. 6 Applied horizontal forcing and boundary conditions for the unit cell extracted from the CHH structure, (a) Load distribution on strut CB, (b) Load distribution on strut BA.

$$\begin{cases} R_{CB} = R_C \cos(\theta) + P \sin(\theta) \\ P_{CB} = P \cos(\theta) - R_C \sin(\theta) \\ M_{CB} = -M_C - R_C r(1 - \cos(\theta)) + Pr \sin(\theta) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, from the force analysis in Fig. 6(b), the axial force (R_{BA}), shear force (P_{BA}) and bending moment (M_{BA}) on the strut, BA can be listed as

$$\begin{cases} R_{BA} = P \\ P_{BA} = F \\ M_{BA} = M_C + M_B + Pr \sin(\theta) - R_C r(1 - \cos(\theta)) - Fx \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The elastic strain energy stored in the unit cell ABCD is composed of two components.

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{CB} &= \int_0^\theta \frac{R_{CB}^2}{2E_1A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{kP_{CB}^2}{2G_{12}A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{M_{CB}^2}{2E_1I} r d\theta \\
&= \int_0^\theta \frac{(R_C \cos(\theta) + P \sin(\theta))^2}{2E_1A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{k(P \cos(\theta) - R_C \sin(\theta))^2}{2G_{12}A} r d\theta + \\
&\int_0^\theta \frac{(-M_C - R_C r(1 - \cos(\theta)) + Pr \sin(\theta))^2}{2E_1I} r d\theta \\
U_{BA} &= \int_0^L \frac{R_{BA}^2}{2E_1A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{kP_{BA}^2}{2G_{12}A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{M_{BA}^2}{2E_1I} dx \\
&= \int_0^L \frac{P^2}{2E_1A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{kF^2}{2G_{12}A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{(M_C + M_B + Pr \sin(\theta) - R_C r(1 - \cos(\theta)) - Fx)^2}{2E_1I} dx
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Due to symmetric boundary conditions, vertical displacement and in-plane rotation in point C, i.e. v_C and θ_C and rotation in point B, θ_B must be restricted. Then;

$$\begin{cases}
v_C = \frac{dU_{CB}}{dR_C} + \frac{dU_{BA}}{dR_C} = 0 \\
\theta_C = \frac{dU_{CB}}{dM_C} + \frac{dU_{BA}}{dM_C} = 0 \\
\theta_B = \frac{dU_{CB}}{dM_B} + \frac{dU_{BA}}{dM_B} = 0
\end{cases} \tag{13}$$

Simultaneous solution of the abovementioned three relations results in the values of vertical reaction force R_C , bending moment M_C and bending moment M_B as a function of the applied concentrated load of P as

$$\begin{cases}
R_C = f_3(P) \\
M_C = f_4(P) \\
M_B = f_5(P)
\end{cases} \tag{14}$$

Replacing reaction force R_C , bending moment M_C and bending moment M_B into obtained strain energy results in

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{CB} &= \int_0^\theta \frac{(f_3(P) \cos(\theta) + P \sin(\theta))^2}{2E_1A} r d\theta + \int_0^\theta \frac{k(P \cos(\theta) - f_3(P) \sin(\theta))^2}{2G_{12}A} r d\theta + \\
&\int_0^\theta \frac{(-f_4(P) - f_3(P) r(1 - \cos(\theta)) + Pr \sin(\theta))^2}{2E_1I} r d\theta \\
U_{BA} &= \int_0^L \frac{P^2}{2E_1A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{kF^2}{2G_{12}A} dx + \int_0^L \frac{(f_4(P) + f_5(P) + Pr \sin(\theta) - f_3(P) r(1 - \cos(\theta)) - Fx)^2}{2E_1I} dx
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Now, the horizontal deflection of point C could be obtained by differentiation of the total strain energy related to horizontal load P as

$$u_c = \left(\frac{dU_{BA}}{dP} + \frac{dU_{CB}}{dP} \right)_{F=0} \tag{16}$$

Having the horizontal deflection and applied load, the horizontal stiffness of the structure can be obtained as

$$E_x = \frac{P(L - r(1 - \cos(\theta)) + L_2)}{BH u_c} \tag{17}$$

It should be noted that in Eq. (17), the horizontal deflection at the point of applied loading i.e. u_c can be evaluated by Eq. (16).

2.3 Poisson's ratio

Poisson's ratio of the unit cell can be calculated by determining the horizontal displacement of point C. After determining the amount of displacement u_c (Eq. (16)), normal strain in the x direction determined as Eq. (18).

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{u_c}{2(L + L_2 - r(1 - \cos(\theta)))} \quad (18)$$

Poisson's ratio is defined as the negative ratio of the transverse strain (strain perpendicular to the direction of the applied load) on point B to the longitudinal strain (strain parallel to the direction of the applied load). It should be noted that the unit cell's vertical strain can easily be obtained by imposing a dummy load P_d on point B. Having u_y^B , the vertical strain can be evaluated as

$$\varepsilon_y = \frac{u_y^B}{r \sin(\theta)} \quad (19)$$

Therefore, Poisson's ratio is obtained according to Eq. (20).

$$\nu_{xy} = -\frac{\varepsilon_y}{\varepsilon_x} = -\frac{2u_y^B(L + L_2 - r(1 - \cos(\theta)))}{r \sin(\theta) u_c} \quad (20)$$

This relation means that the length and angle of struts could affect the Poisson's ratio.

2.4 Determining the relative density

The relative density (ρ^*) of a cellular structure is defined as the ratio of the density of the cellular solid to that of the solid material from which it is constructed. The relative density of a cellular structure is determined by calculating the ratio of the unit cell volume ($V_{\text{Unit cell}}$) to the unit cell total volume (V_T). It is a commonly used method to characterize various cellular structures and is a key factor in determining their mechanical properties [37]. Considering the unit cell dimensions shown in Fig. 2(b), the unit cell's volume and total volume can be determined according to Eq. (2) and Eq. (3).

$$V_{\text{Unit cell}} = 2tB(2L + 2L_2 + 2r\theta) \quad (21)$$

$$V_T = 4B(L + L_2 - r(1 - \cos(\theta))) (r \sin(\theta)) \quad (22)$$

According to Eq. (21) and Eq. (22), the relative density of the CHH honeycomb is obtained in Eq. (23).

$$\rho^* = \frac{\tilde{\rho}}{\rho_s} = \frac{V_{\text{Unit cell}}}{V_T} = \frac{t(L + L_2 + r\theta)}{L + L_2 - r(1 - \cos(\theta)) (r \sin(\theta))} \quad (23)$$

The obtained relative density (ρ^*) is a key parameter for material or geometry selection.

2.5 Calculation of plateau force

The previous sections obtained the elastic modulus in horizontal and vertical directions analytically. In this section, an analytical model will be developed to get the plateau force in the nonlinear region that can be used to analyze the crash strength of curved unit cells subjected to compressive loads. According to Fig. 7(a), at the start of the compression process, the unit cell is assumed to be located in its original position with no distortions with the height of H . Then, by applying compressive loading during the crushing, the upper cell wall moves toward the bottom one. At the densification state, the strut AB bends at an angle of $\Delta\theta$ toward curved strut BC, and the total height of the cell reaches H_f (Fig. 7(b)). It is worth noting that the densification state is defined as the status in which the re-entrant unit cell reaches its minimum height and is determined by the summation of its strut thickness. At the densification state, the relative displacement along direction 2 and the bending angle of the representative cell related to its initial position can be evaluated as

$$u_y = H - H_f = 2r\sin(\theta) - 2t - 4r\sin^2(\theta/2) \quad (24)$$

and

$$\Delta\theta = \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta \quad (25)$$

Employing the energy conservation theory, by equating the external work with the plastic energy dissipation, the plateau stress can be obtained by

$$F_1 u_y = 8M_p \Delta\theta \quad (26)$$

M_p is the struts' plastic bending moment, which can be expressed as $M_p = \sigma_{ys} b t^2 / 4$ for the rigid perfect-plastic beams with a rectangular cross-section. The external work must be evaluated for eight plastic angles at the ends of four straight walls marked by the eight small red circles in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Compression process of one unit cell of the CHH structure, (a) initial configuration, and (b) idealized densification.

Finally, the plateau load of the CHH unit cell can be defined by Eq.(27) as

$$F_1 = \frac{2\sigma_{ys} b t^2 (\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta)}{2r\sin(\theta) - 2t - 4r\sin^2(\theta/2)} \quad (27)$$

Where σ_{ys} is the yield stress of the material.

Having the plateau force F_1 , the plateau stress σ_p can be obtained as

$$\sigma_p = \frac{\sigma_{ys} b t^2 (\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta)}{(2r\sin(\theta) - 2t - 4r\sin^2(\frac{\theta}{2}))(L - r(1 - \cos(\theta)) + L_2)} \quad (28)$$

The obtained plateau stress σ_p is a pivotal parameter to examine the energy absorption based on the geometrical parameters of structure.

3. Multi-objective optimization

3.1 Evaluation indicators

When the CHH structure is used to absorb energy in the vertical direction, the in-plane vertical stiffness and plateau stress are the most dominant parameters which affect the structure's efficiency. Therefore, the maximum values of stiffness and plateau stress in the direction of applied loading are targeted as the major indicators to evaluate the absorbed energy performance of the proposed structures.

3.2 Sensitivity analysis of parameters

Due to the large number of parameters of the proposed CHH structure, the sample size will increase in multi-objective optimization. Consequently, conducting a sensitivity geometrically analysis for each parameter is imperative to mitigate computational costs before engaging in the multi-objective optimization process. This analysis examines each parameter's impact on energy absorption performance. Typically, the sensitivity of design variables to design objectives can be quantified using a sensitivity index [38], which is defined as follows:

$$S_{n_i} = \left. \frac{\partial f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)}{\partial z_i} \right|_{\text{NOP}} \frac{z_i}{f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)} \approx \frac{\text{percentage change in } f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)}{\text{percentage change in } z_i}$$

$$= \frac{\frac{\Delta f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)}{f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)}}{\frac{\Delta z_i}{z_i}} \quad (29)$$

Where $f(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N)$ stands for the function of the design objective, and z_i stands for design variables, including L, L_2, r, θ and t . This paper introduces the comprehensive sensitivity index $G(n_i)$, which can consider both vertical equivalent modulus E_y and plateau stress σ_p design objectives and uses the weight coefficient to evaluate each variable sequentially. $G(n_i)$ is defined as

$$G(n_i) = w_1 |S_{E_y}| + w_2 |S_{\sigma_p}| \quad (30)$$

Where w_1 and w_2 are the weights of E_y and σ_p , respectively, while satisfying the relationship of $w_1 + w_2 = 1$. It is necessary to select the weight coefficient according to the importance of the optimization objective during multi-objective optimization. However, there is no standardized method for weight selection in actual conditions. For a lattice structure applicable as an energy absorber, σ_p represents the ability to produce plastic deformation, while E_y represents the applicability, and they are mutually binding and equally important. Therefore, the values of w_1 and w_2 were both set to 0.5 in this paper.

Fig. 8 Sensitivity index variations for design parameters of CHH honeycomb structure.

According to the Eqs. (29) and (30), the sensitivity indices and the comprehensive sensitivity indices of each design variable to the two optimization objectives were calculated as shown in Fig. 8. The design variables with high sensitivity index greatly influence the optimization goal. Therefore, the parameters

θ , r , and t were relatively important design variables in multi-objective optimization, and the design objective function is highly sensitive to these variables. It should be noted that the considered value for each design parameter is based on the assumed values mentioned in Table 1. The evaluated equivalent vertical stiffness and plateau stress for the considered geometrical parameters are 1.75 MPa and 196 Pa, respectively.

Table 1 considered geometrical parameters for sensitive analysis.

L (mm)	L_2 (mm)	θ (deg)	r (mm)	t (mm)	B (mm)
15	15	45	7.07	2.5	2

3.3 The optimization framework

According to the sensitivity analysis results, four parameters, including the r , θ and t , were selected as the main design variables, while L and L_2 were still considered secondary factors. The objective function of the optimization problem was the maximum value of E_y and σ_p . As a result, the mathematical model of multi-objective optimization for SHS unit cell was presented as

$$\min\{-E_y, -\sigma_p\} \quad (31)$$

$$\text{s. t.} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 5^\circ < \theta < 70^\circ \\ 7 \text{ mm} < L < 35 \text{ mm} \\ 15 \text{ mm} < L_2 < 70 \text{ mm} \\ 1 \text{ mm} < t < 5 \text{ mm} \\ 10 \text{ mm} < r\theta < 250 \text{ mm} \\ L < r(1 - \cos(\theta)) \\ 10 \text{ mm} < 4L + 2L_2 + 4r\theta < 150 \text{ mm} \\ B = 10 \text{ mm} \end{array} \right. \quad (32)$$

This paper employs closed-form analytical relations to optimize objective functions of stiffness and plateau stress. Based on the established analytical model for the stiffness and plateau stress, NSGA-II multi-objective optimization of MATLAB started from the random position in the design space.

4. Experimental and numerical validation

4.1 Experimental tests

To examine the accuracy of developed relations, including the equivalent stiffness in vertical and horizontal directions of the introduced structure, the sample tests must be fabricated using the fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D printing machine for specified geometric parameters. For this purpose, the Polylactic Acid (PLA) filament with a 1.75 mm diameter is used to prepare all specimens. During the 3D printing procedure, the temperature of the nozzle and building plate was set to 200° C and 60° C, respectively. All samples were manufactured using this 3D printing setup.

4.1.1 Properties of raw material

To measure the properties of the raw material, dog bone specimens of PLA are printed using FDM. ASTM-D638 standards are utilized to conduct tensile tests on the specimens [39]. A minimum of three samples are tested for each test. Using an Instron 5500R machine, tensile tests are conducted at a 5 mm/min fixed crosshead speed. The stress-strain response of standard coupon tests is illustrated in Fig. 10. The obtained mechanical properties of PLA under the performed tensile tests are mentioned in Table 2.

Fig. 9 The printed dog bone specimens type IV of PLA tensile test based on ASTM-D638 standard [39].

Fig. 10 Stress-strain response of dog bone specimens of PLA based on ASTM-D638 standard.

Table 2 Obtained material properties of PLA using tensile test standard.

E (GPa)	ν	σ_y (MPa)	ϵ_c	σ_{ut} (MPa)
1.81 ± 1	0.3	25.5 ± 1.2	0.16 ± 0.01	18.5 ± 0.5

4.1.2 Comparison between the experimental and analytical results

To obtain the horizontal and vertical stiffnesses of the proposed structure, different cellular structures with diverse geometrical parameters are 3D printed (Fig. 11). It should be noted that the considered values for the angles of r and θ as the major geometrical design parameters are selected in the range of optimal values for the best stiffness and energy absorption based on the results of optimization code. Table 3 reflects the considered values for the geometrical parameters of the cellular unit cell in coupon tests of each direction. A universal test machine subjected the specimens to compressive tests at 5 mm/min speed. A minimum of two samples were tested for each direction, and a stress-strain curve was extracted to calculate the elastic modulus.

Fig. 11 Cellular structures printed for compressive testing loading (a) Horizontal HL, (b) Vertical VL, (c) Horizontal HK, (d) Vertical VK, (e) Horizontal HS, (f) Vertical HS.

Table 3 Considered geometrical parameters for 3D printing structures in horizontal and vertical directions.

		L (mm)	L_2 (mm)	r (mm)	θ (deg)	t (mm)	B (mm)	Total dimension (mm ³)
Type L	HL	2.49	3	8.18	15	0.6	10.12	158×22×10.12
	VL	2.49	3	8.18	19.41	0.5	10.17	109.7×39.66×10.17
Type S	HS	2	3	12.75	10	0.60	9.84	109.76×30.22×9.84
	VS	2	3	12.75	12.46	0.41	7.92	149.78×21.90×7.92
Type K	HK	3	2.5	4.82	25	0.57	10.1	96×59×10.1
	VK	3	2.5	4.82	34.76	0.63	8.6	148×25×8.6

Two specimens were used for each direction to experimentally measure the effect of Young's modulus on the mechanical properties of cellular structures. To apply a uniform load to the structures, two steel plates are used at the top and bottom of the specimens with a depth of 20 mm. An in-plane uniaxial compression load is imposed on the specimens utilizing an Instron 5500R machine. The upper jaw displacement speed for the quasi-static load was 5 mm/min. Fig. 12 shows strain-stress curves for baseline cellular structures in horizontal and vertical directions. The obtained results show that the elastic modulus in the vertical direction significantly surpasses that in the horizontal direction.

Employing the extended relation for equivalent stiffnesses in different directions will examine the accuracy of the relation with the performed test results. For this purpose, the geometrical parameters mentioned in Table 3 will be employed. The comparison between both approaches is depicted in

Table 4. According to the obtained result for specimen type L, the difference between calculated and measured values is 10.8% for the horizontal direction and 4.6% for the vertical direction. Meanwhile, for specimen type S, the difference between calculated and measured values is 13.9% for horizontal and 7.6% for vertical directions.

Fig. 12 Compressive stress-strain response for printed CHH structures: (a) Horizontal type L-HL, (b) Vertical type L-VL, (c) Horizontal type K-HK, (d) Vertical type K-VK, (e) Horizontal type S-HS, (f) Vertical type S-VS.

Table 4 Comparison of the obtained vertical stiffness of SHS structure between analytical and experimental approaches.

Stiffness	Analytical (MPa)	Experimental (MPa)	Difference (%)
VL	146	131.75	10.8
HL	73.23	70	4.6
VS	141.34	124	13.9
HS	58.85	54.68	7.6
VK	148.08	138.44	6.9
HK	86.47	83.02	3.9

Similarly, for specimen type K, the difference between calculated and measured values is 6.9% for the horizontal direction while it is 3.9% for the vertical direction. These findings demonstrate that the analytical model reasonably predicts the equivalent mechanical properties in cellular structures. The calculated values exhibit a good agreement with the measurements, indicating the reliability and accuracy of the analytical approach in predicting the mechanical properties of the studied lattice structures.

4.2 Numerical simulation methodology

This study uses a numerical method to validate the material properties and plateau stress. It is important to note that linear FEA is used to verify the equivalent elastic moduli, while nonlinear FEA is necessary to determine the plateau force. To achieve this, a developed numerical approach is utilized to assess the effects of damage or plasticity modes on the CHH unit cell's compressive response, fabricated with pure and reinforced PLA materials. The ABAQUS explicit solver (version 6.14.3) is employed for simulation purposes. Specifically, the explicit solver is used to simulate the nonlinear response of the CHH unit cell. 3D elements with 8-node reduced integration (C3D8R) are used to discretize the structure struts to avoid a shear-locking effect. Fig. 13 illustrates the local coordinate system aligned with the fiber direction in each strut and the mesh discretization of the lattice unit cell subjected to compressive vertical force. To account for the contact condition between rigid surfaces and the lattice structure, a coefficient of friction of 0.2 is considered, and the penalty method is employed. This friction coefficient is chosen so that the maximum contact force in the numerical simulation aligns with the experimental results. Moreover, the self-contact method is utilized to prevent strut penetration under compression load. A mesh convergence analysis is conducted with a mesh size of 0.1 mm to ensure reasonable adjustments and reliable simulations, achieving sufficient accuracy while reducing computational costs.

Fig. 13 (a) Considered local coordinates system align with the fiber direction and (b) the mesh discretization in CHH unit cell.

The material behavior of CHH specimens fabricated with PLA and composite material is modeled using elastic-plastic (damage) data. Using the VUSDFLD subroutine, the material properties of the associated element are degraded when the stress reaches the failure level.

4.2.1 Comparison between the numerical and analytical results

As mentioned before, to examine the accuracy of presented relations for equivalent material properties, especially for the *structures made with composite materials*, the ABAQUS FE software is used to investigate the linear behavior of the proposed structure. For this purpose, the simulation is done using 3D FEs, and the C3D8R element (An 8-node linear brick, reduced integration, hourglass control) is

utilized. The following geometrical parameter data and material properties mentioned in Table 5 and Table 6 are considered for the numerical analysis.

Table 5 Considered geometrical parameters for verification via FE.

Case	L (mm)	L_2 (mm)	r (mm)	θ (deg)	t (mm)	B (mm)
1	2	2	25.82	5.25	0.5	1
2	1.5	2	6.58	20.25	0.5	1
3	3	2.5	5.32	25.25	0.5	1
4	2.49	3	8.68	15.28	0.5	1
5	3.5	2.5	4.5	30.25	0.5	1
6	3.5	4.35	6.6	31.50	0.2	2

Table 6 Considered material properties for the fiber and matrix of SHS lattice structure.

E_f (GPa)	ν_f	E_m (GPa)	ν_m
61.83	0.18	2.88	0.33

It should be noted that to obtain the equivalent material properties of composite material, having the fiber volume fraction of V_f , the rule of the mixture is employed to evaluate the axial stiffness E_1 and in-plane Poisson's ratio of ν_{12} as

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f) \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_f V_f + \nu_m (1 - V_f) \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Furthermore, to obtain E_2 and G_{12} , the Halpin- Tsai (H-T) equations are used as

$$M/M_m = (1 + \xi \eta V_f) / (1 - \eta V_f) \quad (34)$$

Where

$$\eta = \frac{\left(\frac{M_f}{M_m}\right) - 1}{\left(\frac{M_f}{M_m}\right) + \xi} \quad (35)$$

Where M represents E_2 or G_{12} , M_f represents E_f or G_f and M_m represents E_m or G_m . The parameter ξ takes the values 1 and 2 for E_2 and G_{12} , respectively. It should be noted that the current 3D printers can fabricate composite structures with a maximum 20% fiber volume fractions in the cases of continuous and chopped fibers. As a result, the obtained results of the present study will be presented for the pure, 10%, and 20% volume fractions of fibers.

4.2.1.1 Vertical stiffness of a conventional structure

At first, for the unit cell fabricated with the pure PLA, by considering the geometrical parameters according to Table 5 and applying 2N vertical load to each cell subjected to the periodic boundary conditions, the vertical displacement is recorded by FE and compared with the analytical results in Table 7.

Table 7 Comparison of the obtained vertical displacement of different CHH unit cells between analytical and FE methods at different geometrical parameters.

Case	Analytical (mm)	Numerical (mm)	Difference (%)
1	1.66e-3	1.81e-3	8.4
2	1.90e-3	2.09e-3	9
3	2.12e-3	2.15e-3	8
4	1.78e-3	1.92e-3	7.2
5	2.39e-3	2.38e-3	0.5
6	1.46e-2	1.23e-2	18

The obtained results reveal a good agreement between the results, and the difference between the analytical and FE results is less than 18%.

In the next stage, by considering the effect of fiber volume fraction on the material properties of unit cell Case 6, the comparison between the analytical and numerical results is illustrated in Table 8. The results reveal a relatively good agreement between the obtained results, and the difference between the analytical and FE results is less than 14%.

Table 8 Comparison of the obtained vertical displacement of CHH unit cell between analytical and FE methods at different volume fractions of fibers.

V_f	Analytical (mm)	Numerical (mm)	Difference (%)
10%	5.23e-3	5.6e-3	6.6
20%	3.32e-3	3.9e-3	14

4.2.1.2 Horizontal stiffness of a conventional structure

Likewise, when applying a horizontal load of 2 N to the unit cells in Cases 1-3 under a periodic boundary condition, the horizontal displacement is recorded using FE analysis and compared with analytical results in Table 9. The comparison shows that the difference between the FE and analytical approaches is less than 9%. Furthermore, the effect of fiber volume fraction on the material properties of unit cell Case 6 is considered, and the comparison between the analytical and numerical results of horizontal stiffness is presented in Table 10. The findings demonstrate a relatively good agreement between the obtained results, with the difference between the analytical and FE results being less than 7%.

Table 9 Comparison of the obtained horizontal displacement of different CHH unit cells between analytical and FE methods at different geometrical parameters.

Case	Analytical (mm)	Numerical (mm)	Difference (%)
1	3.97e-2	3.76e-2	5.5
2	2.29e-2	2.42e-2	5.3
3	2.15e-2	2.07e-2	4.8
4	2.90e-2	2.94e-2	1.7
5	1.91e-2	1.84e-2	3.8
6	9.86e-2	9.00e-2	8.7

Table 10 Comparison of the obtained horizontal displacement of CHH unit cell between analytical and FE methods at different volume fractions of fibers.

V_f	Analytical (mm)	Numerical (mm)	Difference (%)
10	3.34e-2	3.40e-2	1.7
20	2.04e-2	2.18e-2	6.8

4.2.1.3 Plateau force analysis

A nonlinear FEA will be conducted to verify the accuracy of the extended relationships for plateau force in Eq. (26). This analysis considers the nonlinear response due to damage in both the pure PLA and composite material. The VUSDFLD subroutine in ABAQUS 2017 is used to capture the nonlinear response. By implementing this approach, the nonlinear behavior of the PLA and composite material in the fiber and transverse directions can be taken into account, allowing the use of the Hashin failure criterion to update the composite material properties under various loading conditions. The comparison between the analytical and numerical plateau forces for half of the specified unit cell can be observed in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 Comparison between the obtained plateau force by analytical and FE approaches at different fiber volume fractions.

Fig. 15 Variation of angles of the CHH unit cells with different volume fractions of fibers subjected to the vertical displacement of 2.5 mm obtained by FE: (a) pure PLA, (b) PLA with 10% volume fraction of fibers, (c) PLA with 20% volume fraction of fibers.

It is important to mention that the analytical plateau force is determined based on the change angles measured in the FE analysis, as depicted in Fig. 15 and Table 11. To assess the effect of damage or plasticity, a vertical displacement of 2.5 mm is applied to each unit cell with different volume fractions

of fibers, and the resulting variations in angles are recorded. Notably, the plastic (damage) stress values for Pure PLA, 10%, and 20% are set to 60 MPa, 125 MPa, and 190 MPa, respectively. This implies that for the struts of CHH specimens made with reinforced PLA, the structure is modeled as an orthotropic material with failure stresses of 125 MPa and 190 MPa in the fiber direction for 10% and 20% fiber volume fraction, respectively. Additionally, it should be emphasized that the transverse moduli of elasticity of reinforced PLA, i.e., E_2 and E_3 , are assumed to be equal to the elastic modulus of pure PLA. Also, the values of shear modulus and Poisson's ratios are assumed 3.6 GPa and 0.18, respectively. According to the obtained results in Fig. 14, the estimated plateau force for all cases agrees with the obtained FE results.

Table 11 Evaluation of analytical plateau force using the angle variations in unit cells with different fiber volume fractions.

	$\Delta\theta$	$\Delta\theta'$	θ_2	θ_2'	$\Delta_1=\Delta\theta-\Delta\theta'$	$\Delta_2=\theta_2-\theta_2'$	$\Delta\phi=\Delta_1+\Delta_2$	$\sigma_{ys}(\text{MPa})$	$u_y(\text{mm})$	$F_1(\text{N})$
Pure PLA	56.85	9.73	83.9	58.2	47.12	25.68	72.8	60	2.5	1.21
10%	56.85	15	83.9	52	41.85	31.9	73.75	125	2.5	2.57
20%	56.85	15	83.9	60	41.85	23.9	65.75	190	2.5	3.48

Table 11 reports the evaluated plateau forces for each case according to considered values for yield (failure) stress and angle changes.

5. Discussion on the effectiveness of CHH honeycombs

5.1 Discussion of Pareto front

Using the established analytical model for stiffness and plateau stress (Eq. (9) and Eq. (27)), a multi-objective optimization using NSGA-II in MATLAB 2018 was initiated from random positions within the design space. The optimization process consisted of 200 initial population sizes and 300 iterations, resulting in a maximum population of 60,000. Fig. 16 illustrates the design objective function values for all 60,000 NSGA-II optimization samples, depicted as red dots, for structures made of pure PLA, 10%, and 20% fiber volume fraction. The dot points represent an approximate Pareto front of the optimization results, with the precise front converging to this range. The optimization result illustrated that E_y and σ_p cannot be satisfied simultaneously, which means that improving one will cause the other to degrade. Therefore, the optimal design parameters should be selected from the Pareto front according to the stiffness and plateau stress requirements in real engineering applications.

Fig. 16. Pareto front optimization graph based on the optimized value of vertical stiffness and plateau stress in CHH unit cells with different volume fractions of fibers: ● pure PLA, (b) ● 10% fiber volume fraction and (c) ● 20% fiber volume fraction.

The variation of the values of major geometrical parameters, including r , and θ in the obtained optimum values for vertical stiffness and plateau stress of unit cells fabricated with pure PLA, 10% and 20% fiber volume fractions is illustrated in Fig. 17. The graphs reveal that, for the selection of angle r , in structures fabricated with pure PLA, 10% and 20% fiber volume fraction, a wide range can be considered, which is 18-52 mm, 19-41 mm and 53-80 mm respectively.

Fig. 17. Variation of major geometrical parameters of CHH unit cell as a function of optimized vertical stiffness and plateau stress for (a) pure PLA, (b) 10% fiber volume fraction, (c) 20% fiber volume fraction: ● vertical stiffness, ● plateau stress.

Meanwhile, for the selection of angle θ , in structures fabricated with pure PLA, 10% and 20% fiber volume fraction, a range can be considered, which is 10° - 34° , 16° - 30° and 7° - 11° respectively. In addition, the best selection values for minor geometrical parameters i.e., the lengths of L , and L_2 are reported in

Table 12. It should be noted that the best value for the thickness in all the cases is 5 mm.

Table 12 The range of variation of minor geometrical parameters for optimized analytical plateau force using the angle variations in unit cells with different fiber volume fractions.

	L (mm)	L_2 (mm)
Pure PLA	7.25	16
10% fiber volume fraction	7-7.5	15-15.5
20% fiber volume fraction	7	15

5.2 Parametric study on the equivalent material properties

The obtained relation for the vertical stiffness makes it possible to perform a parametric study to examine the impact of geometrical parameters on the equivalent stiffness of the mentioned structure. For this purpose, having the mentioned constraints in Eq. (1), while the variation of θ is considered between 5° to 40° , the length L is considered between 25 mm to 35 mm. As a result, the circumference of all the probable geometries presented in the following table is fixed with a value of 21.01 mm. It should be noted that the value of strut L_2 is considered 4.35 mm for all the possible shapes.

θ ($^\circ$) \n L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5								
3.0								
3.5								

Fig. 18 Different configurations of unit cells for variation of geometrical parameters in the constant circumference of the CHH unit cell.

5.2.1 Relative density

The results of obtained relative density of diverse unit cell introduced in

Fig. 18 evaluated by Eq. (23) is mentioned in Table 13.

Table 13 Variation of relative density of CHH unit cells.

Relative density of unit cells (ρ^*)								
θ ($^\circ$) \n L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	0.112	0.114	0.116	0.118	0.121	0.124	0.127	0.131
3.0	0.149	0.151	0.153	0.155	0.158	0.161	0.165	0.170
3.5	0.243	0.245	0.248	0.251	0.255	0.259	0.265	0.270

According to the obtained results, at the constant values of θ , enhancement in the values of L results in the rise in the relative density. On the contrary, at the constant values of L , enhancement in the values of θ results in a decrease in the relative density of the unit cell.

5.2.2 Vertical stiffness

The results of vertical equivalent stiffness for three cases of pure, 10%, and 20% volume fractions of fibers are presented in Table 14. As evident, the vertical stiffness is enhanced with a decrease in the angle θ and length L . As a result, the maximum stiffness belongs to the $\theta=5^\circ$ and $L=2.5$ mm. Furthermore, as expected, increasing the fiber volume fraction enhances the equivalent vertical stiffness of the structure.

Table 14 Variation of equivalent vertical stiffness of CHH unit cell at different fiber volume fractions.

E_y (MPa)		Pure PLA							
θ ($^\circ$)	L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	2.5	74.67	54.13	37.18	25.98	18.79	14.07	10.85	8.57
3.0	3.0	73.48	60.09	45.89	34.42	25.99	19.94	15.57	12.34
3.5	3.5	71.61	65.45	56.91	47.92	39.65	32.57	26.73	21.97

E_y (MPa)		$V_f=10\%$							
θ ($^\circ$)	L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	2.5	225.51	161.07	109.37	75.85	54.63	70.80	31.41	24.78
3.0	3.0	221.69	177.68	132.99	98.25	73.41	55.90	43.41	34.31
3.5	3.5	215.87	192.21	161.65	131.71	105.92	85.00	68.48	55.51

E_y (MPa)		$V_f=20\%$							
θ ($^\circ$)	L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	2.5	374.89	264.82	178.34	123.05	88.35	65.85	50.63	39.92
3.0	3.0	368.27	290.83	214.65	156.91	116.39	88.21	68.28	53.84
3.5	3.5	358.40	313.19	257.49	205.38	162.26	128.44	102.38	82.32

5.2.3 Horizontal stiffness

Like the vertical stiffness, the results of horizontal equivalent stiffness for three cases of pure, 10%, and 20% volume fractions of fibers and all the probable geometries mentioned in Fig. 18 are presented in the following tables.

Table 15 Variation of equivalent horizontal stiffness of CHH unit cell at different fiber volume fractions.

E_x (MPa)		Pure PLA							
θ ($^\circ$)	L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	2.5	0.43	0.92	1.38	1.71	1.91	2.04	2.10	2.13
3.0	3.0	1.39	2.68	4.23	5.67	6.84	7.74	8.42	8.92
3.5	3.5	9.88	14.45	21.08	28.75	36.61	44.11	50.99	57.15

E_x (MPa)		$V_f=10\%$							
θ ($^\circ$)	L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	2.5	1.30	2.77	4.15	5.12	5.73	6.08	6.27	6.35
3.0	3.0	4.21	8.10	12.72	16.93	20.32	22.89	24.80	26.21
3.5	3.5	29.29	43.05	62.72	85.00	107.34	128.20	146.93	163.44

E_x (MPa)		$V_f=20\%$							
θ ($^\circ$)	L (mm)	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	2.5	2.17	4.61	6.88	8.47	9.46	10.03	10.33	10.46
3.0	3.0	7.00	13.46	21.05	27.89	33.35	37.45	40.47	42.69
3.5	3.5	48.02	70.87	103.13	139.12	174.62	207.27	236.17	261.36

As it is evident, contrary to the vertical direction, the horizontal stiffness increases with the angle θ and length L rise. As a result, the maximum stiffness belongs to the $\theta=40^\circ$ and $L=3.5$ mm.

5.2.4 Poisson's ratio

In this section, using Eq. (20), the results of equivalent Poisson's ratio for three cases of pure, 10%, and 20% volume fractions of fibers and all the probable geometries mentioned in

Fig. 18 are presented in the following tables. As it is obvious, the Poisson's ratio decreases with a rise in the angle θ and length L . As a result, the least Poisson's ratio belongs to the $\theta=40^\circ$ and $L=3.5$ mm.

Table 16 Variation of equivalent Poisson's ratio of the CHH unit cell at different fiber volume fractions.

$L(\text{mm}) \backslash \theta (^\circ)$	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
2.5	-0.05	-0.10	-0.15	-0.19	-0.24	-0.28	-0.32	-0.35
3.0	-0.08	-0.16	-0.24	-0.31	-0.38	-0.45	-0.52	-0.59
3.5	-0.15	-0.29	-0.44	-0.58	-0.72	-0.87	-1.10	-1.17

5.3. Positioning of CHH honeycombs in the Ashby Chart

An Ashby chart for the effective vertical elastic modulus of SHS honeycombs can be found in Fig. 19. In this chart, the horizontal axis represents the relative density ρ^* and the vertical axis corresponds to the effective vertical modulus $\bar{E} = \frac{\bar{E}}{E_s}$ in a log-log scale. The design region achievable is highlighted and presented next to other design regions for honeycombs [40]-[41] and foams [42] found in the literature. This chart can be used for topology selection, similar to its conventional use in material selection. In general, the relative density-effective modulus relation is $\bar{E} = C\rho^{*n}$, where C is a constant and the exponent n usually ranges between 1 and 3. This is represented in a log-log scale as a line with a slope equal to n . The upper bound of this design region corresponds to the square lattice [43], where $\bar{E} = \frac{\rho^*}{2}$ therefore, $n = 1$. As the relative contribution of bending increases, n also increases, resulting in a larger slope, up to $n = 3$ as shown in the lower bound in Fig. 19.

Fig. 19 Ashby chart: the design region achievable by CHH structure with constant circumference is highlighted.

For the presented topologies in

Fig. 18, in which the circumference of cells is constant, the design regions of $\bar{E} - \rho^*$ for structures fabricated with pure PLA and PLA reinforced with 10% and 20% volume fractions of glass are highlighted on the Ashby chart. The obtained results for both pure and reinforced PLA reveal the surprising response of the CHH structure at constant circumference, which exhibits the ideal bending-dominated behavior similar to the foams based on the selection of different angle θ and length for the horizontal strut L .

6. Concluding remarks

This study introduced a parametric study for stiffness analysis of CHH auxetic honeycomb for the first time. The shape of the proposed lattice structure is prone to be produced as an excellent candidate structure for 3D printing manufacturing via pure and reinforced filaments. Using the energy method, the equivalent stiffness of vertical and horizontal directions was evaluated and compared with the performed experiments by extracting a unit cell. Furthermore, at the densification state of a unit cell, by employing the energy conservation theory and equating the external work with the plastic energy dissipation, the plateau stress of the proposed honeycomb was evaluated and compared with the nonlinear FE code. Then, a parametric study examined the variation of effective elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, and the relative density as a function of geometrical parameters, including the angle of struts in a constant circumference. Based on the work carried out, the conclusions can be stated as follows:

- Unlike the conventional lattice structure like arrowhead honeycombs, the proposed structure has the feature that by changing the length and angle of the horizontal and oblique struts, special mechanical properties can be achieved in the longitudinal and transverse directions.
- In addition, one of the most important advantages of the proposed geometry is its ability to be produced using the 3D printing manufacturing employing the reinforced filament, the results of which will be published in future research.
- The variation of dimensionless effective modulus versus the relative density in Ashby Chart exhibited the surprising response of the CHH structure at different geometries and material properties, which covers a spectrum responses like the ideal bending-dominated behaviors based on the selection of different angles and length of struts.
- Finally, based on the established analytical model for the stiffness and plateau stress, GA multi-objective optimization performed from the random position in the design space, and the values of geometrical parameters were defined for the optimum values of objective functions of stiffness and plateau stress in the Pareto front chart.

The presented results open the possibilities for smart material and geometry selection in designing high-performance lattice structures suitable for energy absorption in real practical applications.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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